

1 **MAP3K6 functions in compensatory feedback signaling during clinical interventions featuring use**
2 **of the VEGF-A inhibitor bevacizumab.**

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7 Clinical interventions featuring administration of a vascular endothelial growth factor inhibitor
8 (bevacizumab) will generally universally exhibit rebound or compensatory growth factor signaling occurring
9 through specific activation of kinase and phosphatase signal transduction enzymes. Compensatory growth
10 factor signaling enabled by kinase or phosphatase activation supports resistance during the treatment of
11 cancer in humans. We describe here activation of the MAP kinase *MAP3K6* in humans following treatment
12 with bevacizumab (Avastin).

13 Citations

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16 MAPK pathway activation. *Nature medicine*, 25(9), pp.1422-1427.